

The dipole in quantised space

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The model of quantised space is not popular because experimental physics is phenomenological based. So if we stop to focus on local phenomena we are forced to change the way we think about reality. Because in quantised space everything influences everything at exactly the same moment. Fortunately the electromagnetic dipole of a rest mass carrying particle shows the reliability of quantised space as an explanatory model.

Introduction

The schematic image in figure 1 (source [Wikipedia](#)) shows a planet with a magnetic field; a [dipole](#). It is thought that the magnetic field of planets is generated by a difference of rotation velocity between the solid and the more liquid part of the core of the planet. In other words, the planet acts like a generator of electric currents.

figure 1

Rest mass carrying particles have a spin on their own and an electromagnetic dipole too. But it is difficult to imagine that the dipole of a proton originates from its ability to mimic a generator of electric currents. Although there are reports of electric currents without a flow of clear detectable (groups of) electrons or even with a fractionalized electric charge.^{[1][2]} Strong indications that our present knowledge of charged particles is not complete.

One can question the usefulness of more and more descriptions of detected “anomalous” phenomena in the quest for understanding physical reality. Because physical reality is limited to the mutual relations between the local manifes-

tations of the properties of the basic quantum fields (QFT). Mutual relations that don't exist independently from everything around. That is why it is reasonable to focus first on those properties that exist everywhere within the volume of our universe. Like the universal conservation laws, the universal constants and the universal principles. The result – in this paper the model of quantised space^[3] – can be used to understand specific phenomena, like the dipole.

References:

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Particles in quantised space

The cubic structure in figure 2 doesn't represent a realistic appearance of the units of quantised space.^[3] About 74% of the volume of every unit is the internal scalar, the undistorted part of the scalar mechanism of the unit. In other words, the cubic structure is a schematic representation of the structure of quantised space, the underlying structure of the basic quantum fields (universal scalar field, universal topological field and corresponding vector field). In physics these field are known as the Higgs field, the universal electric field and its corresponding magnetic field.

Figure 2 (cross section) shows the vectorisation (v) of vacuum space around the particle in a schematic way and its influence on the density of the universal electric field around the particle (the rasterised concentric shells). The

particle is propagating from position I to position II (see the black arrow). But figure 2 is not the top view of the moving particle, we observe the particle from aside, moving up. The small arrow (\triangleright) shows the direction of its spin.

Quantised space is the rest frame of the universe. Every unit of quantised space has an internal “power” to deform its shape, the internal scalar mechanism. All the changes of the shape of the units are synchronised because every unit has an equal invariant volume. See reference 3 for the details of the geometry of quantised space.

The consequence is that every local observable or detectable change is generated by the structure of quantised space. The linear velocity of the smallest detectable amount of energy – the quantum of energy – is the constant speed of light (c). The particle in figure 2 represents a stable concentration of energy so the structure of quantised space cannot propagate the particle with the speed of light because it is a huge amount of quanta to pass on.

figure 2

Nevertheless, the particle is in motion in relation to the rest frame of the universe. That means that the units at position II in figure 2 have to adapt to the approaching particle. That is why figure 2 is divided in 3 parts. Part A envelopes the units that are influenced by the approaching particle. Part C envelopes the units that are returning to their previous state and part B is the transition zone in between part A and C. Figure 3 shows the situation.

Actually, the units in part A are forced to increase the deformation of their shape and in part C the units return to the average deformation in vacuum space. The transition phase is remarkable because it is aligned with the direction of the spin, perpendicular on the motion of the particle.

figure 3

Figure 3 does not only represent a particle in a schematic way, the image is also suitable for the motion of a planet, a star or even a galaxy. Although the energy concentration of these celestial bodies is enormous in relation to the energy “density” of a unit in vacuum space. The consequence is that a disturbance of e.g. the rotation axis of a planet – like [Uranus](#) nearly 90° tilt in relation to the solar plane – cannot be reversed by the energy density of vacuum space around.

The alignment of the transition phase (B) and the spin of the particle is comparable with the alignment of the solar plane and the rotation of the sun. However, stars originate from the rotational contraction of large cosmic clouds of dust and molecules. That means that all the mass of a star system starts with the same axis of the angular momentum. See the picture in figure 4 of the evolution of the “birth” of a protostar (James Webb Space Telescope).

figure 4

The white dotted line accentuates the visible existence of a rotating disk of dust, etc. around the protostar. The similarities between the alignment of rotation axes and rotational planes of different phenomena at different scale sizes cannot be accidentally. It must have a direct relation with the transition phase B in figure 3.

The fixed amount of topological deformation

The internal scalar mechanism of every unit of the structure of quantised space tries to transform the deformed shape of the unit into an undistorted sphere. The consequence is that every unit is continuously pushing the 12 adjacent units in the joint planes to get this done. But the 12 adjacent units are pushing too.

The units change their shape under invariant volume so if we want to describe their mutual relations – energy in physics – we have to express the differences with the help of surface area. In other words, the Planck constant can be interpreted as a fixed amount of topological deformation. Not a solitary local deformation because every deformation under invariant volume is a duality (see reference 3, figure 10). So every unit transforms its shape – synchronous with all the other units – with an amount of $\frac{1}{2} h$ during $1 t_q$.

figure 5

Energy as (a multiple of) a fixed amount of topological deformation that can be exchanged with other units around has a limited velocity of linear propagation, the constant speed of light (c). There is also the synchronisation of the redistribution of quanta between all the units of quantised space. Therefore, a unit with a high surplus of deformation cannot push away the whole surplus at once. Quantum time is a constant (t_q) in the model of quantised space because of the invariant and equal volume of every unit. The consequence is that local concentrations of energy (mass) have a reduced velocity – the propagation within the structure of quantised space – in relation to the linear pass on of 1 quantum of energy.

Figure 5 shows the process of energy concentration in vacuum space. The arrows represent the direction of the quanta transfer under influence of the “push” of the scalar mechanism of the involved units, so it is about local changes of the universal electric field.

A further concentration of energy will result in a decrease of a scalar of the Higgs field. It facilitates the concentration of more energy. But the decrease of the radius of a scalar will vectorize the Higgs field around the created particle and all the vectors point to the decreased scalar. These vectors are drawn in a schematic way (v) in figure 2 and 3.

figure 6

The result is an increasing energy density towards the particle – the concentric circles in figure 2 and 3 – and some kind of a loop of quanta transfer by the units of quantised space in vacuum space around the particle.

Figure 6 shows a static unit without any topological deformation. The blue arrows symbolise the possible topological deformation in each joint plane. If we imagine that the unit in figure 6 is part of the process of energy concentration in figure 5 it is obvious that the quanta transfer will be anti-clockwise. If there is no dominant vector influence around the topological transformations of the shape of a unit are distributed over all the joint planes. But if there is a dominant vector influence – like the vectors in figure 2 and 3 – and a large concentration of energy (the particle) the unit has no longer the “freedom” to transform its shape in every direction. So it seems like there is a resistance (x) to deform in the direction of the particle. See the graph in figure 7.

The supposed loop of quanta around the particle represents *resultant motion*. Resultant motion is comparable with the linear velocity of an alternating current. The velocity of the involved electrons is high but the linear velocity of all the electrons together is quite slow.

figure 7

However, the resultant motion of the quanta transfer around the particle needs concentric “planes” of units with nearly the same type of topological deformation. See part B in figure 2 and 3. In other words, the phase transition between the increase (A) and the decrease of topological deformation (C) facilitates a kind of quanta transfer in the plane (B) perpendicular to the motion of the particle.

The magnetic dipole

If the particle in figure 3 moves from position I to position II all the shapes of the units above the particle are forced to increase their deformation. It is like a balloon that is pressed from 2 sides. So the balloon will expand its shape in the other directions. The symmetry of the forced deformation depends on the position of the unit in relation to the trajectory of the particle (I → II). But during the motion of the particle the increasing deformation doesn't stop. It goes on and on till the transition phase B arrives.

Copy figure 3

If the unit is at a position right in between I and II it will be forced to become part of the topological deformation of the particle itself before it will decrease its deformation in C.

The increasing topological deformation in 1 joint plane of 2 adjacent units – see figure 8 – shows that an increase of deformation results in an increase of the vector in the point of contact between the 2 scalars. Because the surface of the scalar of the left unit is partly bare by the “push” by the unit on the right side. If the topological deformation decreases the magnitude of the vector will decrease too. If the focus is on the particle it seems like the generated vectors move in closed loops from part A to part C (figure 3). Like the image of the dipole in figure 1.

figure 8

Figure 9 shows the cross section of a magnetic field. The arrows don't represent all the existing vectors so these arrows represent *resulting vectors*. Vectors that represent an evolving local change of the electromagnetic field. I have drawn the mediating scalars of the Higgs field too and the blue background represents the universal electric field.

figure 9

It is obvious that the vectors of the magnetic dipole are resultant vectors that also represent an evolving local change of the electromagnetic field. Be aware that the vectors (v) in figure 3 are generated by the scalars of the Higgs field in vacuum space around the particle. Their influence on the universal electric field are the schematic concentric circles

(energy density = amount of topological deformation). So it is for sure that the vectors (v) and the energy density of the universal electric field around the particle (concentric circles) are co-moving with the particle in motion.

figure 10

I have changed figure 3 with the help of figure 9. The result is the schematic figure 10. The white arrow shows the direction of the motion of the particle (upwards). The black arrows represent the direction of the generated resultant vectors by the motion of the particle in quantised space.

Figure 7 shows that the “freedom to deform in every direction” of the units under influence of dominant vectors is not linear (the concentric circles in figure 2, 3). That means that further from the particle the “freedom” of the units on the approaching and departing particle de/increases. Not at least because a sideways transformation of a unit in the red part of the image is in line with the aim of the scalar mechanism of the units (minimising its surface area). In the blue part the situation is opposite to the red part of the image. In the blue part all the units try to “push” the huge topological deformation away (upwards in figure 10).

figure 11

The existence of the transition zone/phase raises a question about its influence on the direction of the vectors of the

magnetic dipole (figure 11). Because no unit in quantised space can change its shape independently from the adjacent units and other units around.

The influence of the transition zone of the proton on the internal structure of an Hydrogen atom – proton and electron – is not clear. It is impossible to find a reliable clarification without insight in the origin of electrons and the mechanism behind the electric charge. Anyway it shows that my previous attempts to understand the electric charge with the help of the duality of the surplus/deficit of energy – because of the creation of rest mass carrying particles – must be wrong.^{[4][5][6]}

Nevertheless, the topic must be solved because there exists no accepted clarification for the mechanism behind the origin of the electric charge.

References:

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5. S.E. Grimm (2024); “Motion and particles” <https://zenodo.org/record/14199251>
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